

PRESS AND INJECTION HYBRID MOLDING OF GF/PP HAT-SHAPED MEMBER AND EVALUATION OF ITS BENDING PROPERTY

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INTRODUCTION

GF RTP : Glass Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics

Affordable cost compared to CFRTP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics)

Press and injection hybrid molding

Press molding: Outer shell laminate continuous fiber reinforced laminate

Injection molding: Rib structure short or long fiber reinforced thermoplastics

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material

GF/PP laminate (TEPEX, Bond Laminates, $V_f = 47\%$, Thickness = 1.5 mm, 2.0mm)

PP pellet (MA3, Japan Polypropylene Co. Ltd)

GF/PP pellet (HG30U, Japan Polypropylene Co. Ltd)

Molding conditions

	Injection material	Injection volume [cm ³]	Cost [US\$]
T0-PP	PP	192	0.32
T1.5-PP		135	12
T2.0-PP		117	2.1
T0-GF/PP	GF/PP	192	0.80
T1.5-GF/PP		135	12
T2.0-GF/PP		117	22

Finite element analysis

Solid Mechanics (Structural Mechanics Module) of COMSOL Multiphysics®

Three-point bending test

Displacement speed: 5.3×10^{-5} m/s

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Load-displacement curves

Maximum load and stiffness of molded parts

Finite element analysis of three-point bending

Load at displacement 0.96 mm of experimental and analyzed result in three-point bending test.

Molded parts after three-point bending test

Cost evaluation of hat-shaped member

GF/PP for injection materials → Low cost and high specific maximum load and specific stiffness

CONCLUSIONS

- Hybrid molded structures using thicker continuous glass fiber reinforced laminate showed higher specific stiffness and the bending stiffness is successfully predicted by the finite analysis.
- Although the difference in the material cost between T1.5-PP and T1.5-GF/PP and between T2.0-PP and T2.0-GF/PP is only 2% and 5%, respectively, the specific stiffness value was 14% and 24% higher for molded products using the GF/PP resin for injection material.